

Ratsional ko‘rinishdagi integrallar va ularning differensiallash usullari orqali yechimlarini topish

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Ushbu maqolada

$$\int R(x, \sqrt[n]{\frac{ax+b}{cx+d}}) dx, \quad ad - bc \neq 0,$$

ratsional ko‘rinishdagi integrallarni differensiallashlar o‘rganilgan.

1^o. $\int R(x, \sqrt[n]{\frac{ax+b}{cx+d}}) dx$ ko‘rinishidagi integrallarni hisoblash. Faraz qilaylik,

$R(u, v)$ ikki o‘zgaruvchining ratsional funksiyasi bo‘lib, a, b, c, d lar haqiqiy sonlar, $n \in N$ bo‘lsin.

Ushbu

$$\int R(x, \sqrt[n]{\frac{ax+b}{cx+d}}) dx, \quad ad - bc \neq 0,$$

ko‘rinishidagi integrallarni qaraymiz. Bu integral o‘zgaruv-chini almashtirish yordamida ratsional funksiyaning integraliga keladi:

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$$\int R\left(x, \sqrt[n]{\frac{ax+b}{cx+d}}\right) dx = \left| \begin{array}{l} \sqrt[n]{\frac{ax+b}{cx+d}} = t, x = \frac{b-t^n d}{ct^n - a} \\ dx = \frac{(ad-bc)n}{(a-ct^n)^2} t^{n-1} dt \end{array} \right| =$$

$$= \int R\left(\frac{dt^n - b}{a - ct^n}, t\right) \cdot \frac{(ad-bc)nt^{n-1}}{(a-ct^n)^2} dt.$$

1-misol. Ushbu

$$\int \sqrt{\frac{1+x}{1-x}} \cdot \frac{1}{1-x} dx$$

integral hisoblansin.

◀ Bu integralda

$$t = \sqrt{\frac{1+x}{1-x}}$$

almashtirishni bajaramiz. Unda

$$x = \frac{t^2 - 1}{t^2 + 1}, \quad dx = \frac{4tdt}{(t^2 + 1)^2}$$

bo`lib,

$$\int \sqrt{\frac{1+x}{1-x}} \cdot \frac{1}{1-x} dx = 2 \int \frac{t^2 dt}{t^2 + 1}$$

bo`ladi.

Ravshanki,

$$\int \frac{t^2 dt}{t^2 + 1} = t - \arctgt + C.$$

Demak,

$$\int \sqrt{\frac{1+x}{1-x}} \cdot \frac{1}{1-x} dx = 2\sqrt{\frac{1+x}{1-x}} - 2\operatorname{arctg} \sqrt{\frac{1+x}{1-x}} + C \blacktriangleright$$

2^o. $\int R(x, \sqrt{ax^2 + bx + c}) dx$ ko‘rinishidagi integrallarni hisoblash. Bu integralda

a, b, c - haqiqiy sonlar bo‘lib, $ax^2 + bx + c$ kvadrat uchhad teng ildizlarga ega emas.

Qaralayotgan

$$\int R(x, \sqrt{ax^2 + bx + c}) dx \quad (1)$$

integral quyidagi uchta almashtirish yordamida ratsional funksiya integraliga keladi.

a) $a > 0$ bo‘lsin.

(1) integralda ushbu

$$t = \sqrt{ax} + \sqrt{ax^2 + bx + c} \quad (\text{yoki } t = -\sqrt{ax} + \sqrt{ax^2 + bx + c})$$

almashtirishni bajaramiz. U holda

$$ax^2 + bx + c = t^2 - 2\sqrt{a}xt + ax^2,$$

$$x = \frac{t^2 - c}{2\sqrt{at} + b}, \quad dx = \frac{2(\sqrt{at^2 + bt + c}\sqrt{a})}{(2\sqrt{at} + b)^2} dt,$$

$$\sqrt{ax^2 + bx + c} = \frac{\sqrt{at^2 + bt + c}\sqrt{a}}{2\sqrt{at} + b}$$

bo‘ladi.

Natijada

$$\begin{aligned} \int R(x, \sqrt{ax^2 + bx + c}) dx &= \\ &= \int R\left(\frac{t^2 - c}{2\sqrt{at} + b}, \frac{\sqrt{at^2 + bt + c}\sqrt{a}}{2\sqrt{at} + b}\right) \cdot \frac{2(\sqrt{at^2 + bt + c}\sqrt{a})}{(2\sqrt{at} + b)^2} dt \end{aligned}$$

boʻladi.

2-misol. Ushbu

$$\int \frac{dx}{x + \sqrt{x^2 + x + 1}}$$

integral hisoblansin.

◀ Bu integralda

$$t = x + \sqrt{x^2 + x + 1}$$

almashtirishni bajaramiz. Natijada

$$x = \frac{t^2 - 1}{1 + 2t}, \quad dx = 2 \frac{t^2 + t + 1}{(1 + 2t)^2} dt$$

boʻlib,

$$\int \frac{dx}{x + \sqrt{x^2 + x + 1}} = 2 \int \frac{t^2 + t + 1}{(1 + 2t)^2 t} dt$$

boʻladi.

Agar

$$\frac{2(t^2 + t + 1)}{t(1 + 2t)^2} = \frac{2}{t} - \frac{3}{1 + 2t} + \frac{3}{(1 + 2t)^2}$$

boʻlishini eʼtiborga olsak, unda

$$\begin{aligned} \int \frac{dx}{x + \sqrt{x^2 + x + 1}} &= \int \left(\frac{2}{t} - \frac{3}{1 + 2t} + \frac{3}{(1 + 2t)^2} \right) dt = 2 \ln|t| - \frac{3}{2} \ln|1 + 2t| + \frac{3}{2(1 + 2t)} + C = \\ &= 2 \ln|x + \sqrt{x^2 + x + 1}| - \frac{3}{2} \ln|1 + 2x + 2\sqrt{x^2 + x + 1}| + \frac{3}{2(1 + 2x + 2\sqrt{x^2 + x + 1})} + C \end{aligned}$$

boʻlishi kelib chiqadi. ▶

b) $c > 0$ bo`lsin. Bu holda (1) integralda ushbu

$$t = \frac{1}{x}(\sqrt{ax^2 + bx + c} - \sqrt{c})$$

yoki

$$t = \frac{1}{x}(\sqrt{ax^2 + bx + c} + \sqrt{c})$$

almashtirishini bajaramiz. Unda

$$x = \frac{2\sqrt{c} t - b}{a - t^2}, \quad dx = \frac{\sqrt{c}t^2 - bt + \sqrt{c} a}{(a+t)^2} dt, \quad \sqrt{ax^2 + bx + c} = \frac{\sqrt{c} t^2 - bt + a\sqrt{c}}{a - t^2}$$

bo`lib, (1) integral ratsional funksiyaning integraliga keladi:

$$\begin{aligned} \int R(x, \sqrt{ax^2 + bx + c}) dx &= \\ &= \int R\left(\frac{2\sqrt{c}t - b}{a - t^2}, \frac{\sqrt{c}t^2 - bt + a\sqrt{c}}{a - t^2}\right) \left(\frac{\sqrt{c}t^2 - bt + \sqrt{c} a}{(a+t)^2}\right) dt \end{aligned}$$

v) $ax^2 + bx + c$ kvadrat uchhad turli x_1 va x_2 haqiqiy ildizga ega bo`lsin:

$$ax^2 + bx + c = a(x - x_1) \cdot (x - x_2).$$

Bu holda (1) integralda ushbu

$$t = \frac{1}{x - x_1} \sqrt{ax^2 + bx + c}$$

almashtirishni bajaramiz. Natijada

$$x = \frac{-ax_2 + x_1 t^2}{t^2 - a}, \quad \sqrt{ax^2 + bx + c} = \frac{a(x_1 - x_2)}{t^2 - a} t$$

$$dx = \frac{2a(x_1 - x_2)t}{(t^2 - a)^2} dt$$

bo`lib,

$$\int R(x, \sqrt{ax^2 + bx + c}) dx =$$

$$= \int R\left(\frac{-ax_2 + x_1 t^2}{t^2 - a}, \frac{a(x_1 - x_2)}{t^2 - a} t\right) \cdot \frac{2a(x_1 - x_2)t}{(t^2 - a)^2} dt$$

bo`ladi.

3-misol. Ushbu

$$I = \int \frac{x - \sqrt{x^2 + 3x + 2}}{x + \sqrt{x^2 + 3x + 2}} dx$$

integral hisoblansin.

◀ Ravshanki,

$$x^2 + 3x + 2 = (x + 1) \cdot (x + 2).$$

SHuni e`tiborga olib berilgan integralda

$$t = \frac{1}{x+1} \sqrt{x^2 + 3x + 2}$$

almashtirishni bajaramiz. U holda

$$x = \frac{2 - t^2}{t^2 - 1}, \quad dx = -\frac{2tdt}{(t^2 - 1)^2}$$

bo`lib,

$$\int \frac{x - \sqrt{x^2 + 3x + 2}}{x + \sqrt{x^2 + 3x + 2}} dx = \int \frac{-2t^2 - 4t}{(t - 2) \cdot (t - 1) \cdot (t + 1)^3} dt$$

bo`ladi.

Endi

$$\frac{-2t^2 - 4t}{(t-2) \cdot (t-1) \cdot (t+1)^3} = \frac{3}{t-1} - \frac{16}{t-2} - \frac{17}{t+1} + \frac{5}{(t+1)^2} + \frac{1}{(t+1)^3}$$

bo`lishini e`tiborga olib topamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} I &= \int \frac{-2t^2 - 4t}{(t-2) \cdot (t-1) \cdot (t+1)^3} dt = \frac{3}{4} \int \frac{dt}{t-1} - \frac{16}{27} \int \frac{dt}{t-2} - \\ &- \frac{17}{108} \int \frac{dt}{t+1} + \frac{5}{18} \int \frac{dt}{(t+1)^2} + \frac{1}{3} \int \frac{dt}{(t+1)^3} = \frac{3}{4} \ln|t-1| - \\ &- \frac{16}{27} \ln|t-2| - \frac{17}{108} \ln|t+1| - \frac{5}{18} \cdot \frac{1}{t+1} - \frac{1}{6} \cdot \frac{1}{(t+1)^2} + C. \blacktriangleright \end{aligned}$$

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